

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B117
 Date: 27 Jul 2005
 Take Off 07:55:15 12:58:57
 Landing: 11:23:43 15:58:50
 Flight Time 3h28m28s 2h59m53s

Campaign: CWVC
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Chilbolton

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Foster	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	Manchester University
5	Flight Manager	Maureen Smith	FAAM
6	CCN	Paul James	FAAM
7	CCM2/Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	Cloud Physics	Bob Wells	FAAM
9	CVI	Stuart Heath	FAAM
10	CPI	Paul Connolly	Manchester University
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FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b117
 Date: 27th July 05
 Project: CWVC
 Location: Chilbolton

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
073020		Start posn	0.43 kft	000	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
074019		INU	0.43 kft	125	To Navigate
075515		T/O	1.2 kft	036	Cranfield
080051		ASPs	5.0 kft	270	Open
080452		Videos	5.0 kft	234	Start FFC & RFC
082148	082456	Profile 1	10.0 - 7.1 kft	158	1000fpm Interrupt
082553	083031	Profile 1	7.0 - 2.8 kft	239	2600' QNH 1008
083059	084026	Profile 2	2.8 - 12.0 kft	256	2600' , Turn recip
084550	085419	Profile 2	12.1 - 20.0 kft	081	1000fpm Turn @Chlbton
085719	090112	Profile 2	20.1 - 24.0 kft	247	
090956		EVM	23.0 kft	264	No cloud, abort CWVC
092737	093238	Run 1	32.0 kft	245	BBR cold soak
093608	094752	Profile 3	32.0 - 20.0 kft	068	BBR temp. response
095031	100558	Profile 3	20.0 - 4.3 kft	241	
101553	101805	Profile 3	4.3 - 2.9 kft	071	4k'-2k' Q1002
101812	102817	Run 2	2.9 kft	066	2600'
105857		ASPs	11.0 kft	064	Close
112343		Land	0.43 kft	033	Cranfield
113037		Stop posn	0.43 kft	309	52'04.36N, 0'37.48W
113137		INU	0.43 kft	309	To Align

Check weather and Chilbolton radar for 2nd flight

123047		INU	0.43 kft	309	To Navigate
125857		T/O	0.98 kft	109	Cranfield
130558		ASPs	5.0 kft	049	Open
133518	134937	Run 3	10.0 kft	256	Outbound from Chlbton
134017		Videos	10.0 kft	254	Start FFC & RFC
135317	135615	Profile 4	10.0 - 13.0 kft	067	Inbound to Chlbton
135615	140316	Run 4	13.0 kft	077	Inbound to Chlbton
140738	140955	Profile 5	13.0 - 15.0 kft	246	Outbound
140956	141212	Run 5	15.0 kft	249	Outbound
141310	142048	Run 5	15.0 kft	262	ATC Interrupt
142501	142607	Profile 6	15.0 - 16.0 kft	062	Turb prob icing
142607	143353	Run 6	16.0 kft	083	
143809	143903	Profile 7	16.0 - 17.0 kft	240	Outbound
143904	145110	Run 7	17.0 kft	246	Outbound
145322		Cals	17.0 kft	099	JW & Nevz Cals
145455	145600	Profile 8	17.1 - 18.0 kft	082	Inbound
145808		EVM	18.1 kft	000	Rapid turns for ATC
150113	150851	Run 8	18.0 kft	088	To 8nm E of Chlbton
150820		EVM	18.0 kft	075	Ovhd Chilbolton
151235	151338	Profile 9	18.0 - 19.0 kft	246	Outbound
151338	152201	Run 9	19.0 kft	250	JW & Nevz cals
152716	153259	Run 10	15.0 kft	091	Inbound
154000		ASPs	10.0 kft	065	Closed (approx time)
155850		Land	0.45 kft	354	Cranfield
160311		Stop posn	0.44 kft	309	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W
160322		Videos	0.44 kft	309	Stop

B117 Track 27-JUL-05

PROJECT BRIEF: CWVC – mixed-phase cloud studies (KNB 22/07/05)

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems that lie within the temperature regime in which mixed-phase clouds are possible (typically 0 to -30C). In particular, we wish to examine the competing roles of

- primary ice nucleation
- secondary nucleation via the Hallett-Mossop process, in which new ice particles are generated during the riming growth of larger ice particles.
- other secondary ice nucleation mechanisms such as evaporative break-up
- the dependence of these processes on the dynamical environment within the cloud (and in particular the strength of embedded convective updraughts)

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the Camra radar facility at Chilbolton, Hants. The radar may identify features such as embedded convective cells or layers of supercooled liquid water that can be investigated more intensively by the aircraft. Similarly, the aircraft can provide information on microphysical characteristics to aid interpretation of the radar data.

Weather conditions: A stratiform cloud band lying over or to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction, and hence to more easily penetrate identifiable cloud features on successive runs at the same altitude. Note that to avoid interference with Bournemouth airport, Chilbolton is NOT allowed to transmit in the sector 209 to 219 degrees true.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer
- GPS, INU, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud Physics

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 (and SID-2). Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- ADA/CPI – as above
- CCN measurements should be made by filling the alleviator whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest.
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.

Sortie Brief: CWVC – mixed-phase cloud studies
Flight Number: B117

Date: 27th July 2005
M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes and cloud dynamics in stratiform cloud systems in association with Chilbolton radar.

Sortie Location: Within a stratiform cloud system over/to the west of Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign “Radsearch”). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. In this case, the aircraft may fly a small butterfly pattern in which only one of the legs is parallel to the wind direction or radar azimuth. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles. On occasion, the aircraft flight legs may start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so will limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail:

- a) T+0 Take off & climb to FL50 to transit to operating area west of Chilbolton.
- b) T+20 When in a suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl (or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions) or to 1000 ft below the freezing level. Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL280 or to above cloud top (whichever is lower) (40 min)
- c) T+60 Establish start/end points of 40-60km of level flight legs along the azimuth which is being scanned by the radar. Fly these legs at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Duration of each leg ~ 5-10 minutes. Some legs may be extended into the overhead position of Chilbolton when requested from the ground.
- d) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern (see diagram)

- e) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- f) Repeat items c) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.

Sortie de-brief: CWVC2.4 -mixed-phase cloud

Flight Number: B117

Date: 27th July 2005

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes and cloud dynamics in stratiform cloud systems in association with Chilbolton radar (see sortie brief document)

Sortie Location: Within a stratiform cloud system over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility.

Weather conditions:

An occluded front was approaching the south coast of England from the south. The forecast on the previous day suggested the front would move northwards into the experimental area by mid morning, and so an early 9am BST takeoff was scheduled to intercept the required conditions. Overnight the passage of the front northwards stalled and it was still south of the south coast at 06:00z. In the absence of detailed information from the Chilbolton radar, take-off remained as scheduled.

Towards late morning, the rate of progress of the front northwards increased substantially, bringing significant rainfall organised into a band orientated in a west-

east direction, with the features moving from west to east within the band as it moved northwards. These conditions first moved into the CWVC experimental region by midday and remained in the target area until late afternoon.

Flight Summary:

This mission was divided into two flights B117A and B117B.

B117A

Takeoff on B117A occurred at 07:56z (08:56BST) and the aircraft transited to the sortie location at FL100. Most of the ascent to FL100 was in cloud but cloud top (CT) was encountered at around 9200ft (and 1.4°C). A profile descent P1 was carried out (at 1000ft/min) from FL100 to 2600ft, initially on a heading of 158° as the eastern end of the Chilbolton runs was approached from the north, and then on the outbound leg from Chilbolton (travelling W) following an interrupt at FL70 to turn on the heading of 239-256° (the latter being the agreed scanning azimuth of the Chilbolton Radar for CWVC sorties). A profile ascent P2 (1000ft.min) was then started (08:30:59z) continuing on the same heading of 256°. This was interrupted at the western extent of the CWVC runs at FL120 (50.8N, 2.8W), and following a turn to continue the profile on a reciprocal heading of 80°, P2 was recommenced at 08:54:17z. However, CT occurred soon after recommencement, and no cloud could be seen by eye or by CAMRA radar at higher levels (the 35GHz cloud radar was

reported as non-operational). The CT temperature was around -1.3°C . The profile was discontinued at FL240 (following an interrupt at FL220 to turn onto the reciprocal leg).

Without any prospect of cloud above the freezing level the CWVC mission was aborted. The aircraft had approximately 1 hour of fuel left to burn off before it could land so an alternative objective was sought – this turned out to be a BBR cold soak test over the region of the Bristol channel and SW of the channel to an area to the NW of the western tip of Cornwall. A 5minute SLR (Run1) was carried out at FL320 on a heading of 254° followed by a profile descent P3 (at 1000ft/min) on the return leg heading of 68° (interrupted at FL200 and 4000ft to turn onto approximate reciprocal headings), and terminated at 2600ft. Run 2 was then undertaken at 2600ft and a heading of 66° for 8 minutes before climbing back up to FL100 and finally FL110 on the return transit to Cranfield. The aircraft landed at 11:24z

On the return transit the frontal cloud could be seen to the south, but still well south of the CWVC operational area, however the frontal system was forecasted to be overhead in the operational area around Chilbolton and to the west of the radar at around 1:30-2pm BST. The front which had earlier stalled to the south of the south coast was now moving north, with the weather systems moving in a ESE direction along the front. It was therefore decided to conduct a second shorter flight, following aircraft refuelling and a shot debrief, following the same general plan as for the earlier flight.

B117B

Take-off occurred at 12:59z and the aircraft transited to the sortie region at FL100. Initially the transit was in cloud free air or in and out of cloud, but as the sortie region (eastern end of CWVC SLRs) was approached from the north more continuous cloud was encountered. Because of the shortened flight time (3 hours) it was decided to abandon the full profile ascent from below CB up to FL280 (or above CT) and to begin the mission with an initial SLR at FL100 outbound from Chilbolton towards the west. During this leg (starting at 13:35:18 on a heading of 256° at 51.1N, 1.6W) the plan was to communicate with RADSEARCH to ascertain the vertical extent and other microphysical properties of the frontal cloud layer so as to plan the evolution of the sortie to best meet the objectives of the mission. However, the radar suffered a down period during this leg, but had earlier observed the freezing level to be at around 13,000ft, with cloud extending up to 19,500ft. It was noted that at the start of R3 temperatures were about 1.5°C warmer than at the western end (at 13:49:37, 50.9N, 3.0W) where T/Td was $0.13/1.28^{\circ}\text{C}$ (696mbar). During the leg the CPI observed regions containing frozen drops, other mixed phase regions containing melting ice, which was possibly leading to shedding of liquid water at the inlet. Heavy rain was encountered at the end of the run. The radar (CAMRA) came back on line at the end of R3. 2DP reported large particles, 6.5mm in extent which appeared to be wet snow.

Following the turn, the reciprocal leg (077°) back towards Chilbolton commenced with a profile ascent up to FL130 (at 1000ft/min), and continued with a SLR (R4) at

FL130 to the end of the leg (T/Td = -4.23/-3.6°C, 619mbar). During the turn RADSEARCH reported a general CT at around 6km (19,500ft) but with turrets breaking through and ascending to around 9km (but that at 60km range CT was around 4km). During R4 CPI observed sections of “nice” needles/columns, rimed columns and spherical/liquid particles, and regions of purely liquid phase cloud (towards end of run)

The outbound reciprocal leg commenced (at 14:07:36z on a heading of 246°, at 51.0N/1.7W) with an initial profile ascent P5 to FL150, and then continued (14:09:56, 51.0N/1.9W) on a SLR (Run 5) at FL150 initially at -6.9/-6.4°C (572mbar). The CPI was seeing mostly glaciated cloud. A small film of ice was reported on the PMS pods. RADSEARCH reported a region of strong positive zdr and described it as a “good case” to observe. By the end of the run (14:20:48z, 50.8N/3.0W) temperatures had fallen to around -7.5°C. 2D was seeing snow again, and a glimpse of CT was seen during the turn. A couple of turbulence pr5obe parameters were reported as having gone “off-track”. Both SIDs had ice on them, there was ice on the tip of the CVI, and ice was seen on the wings.

The reciprocal inbound leg commenced (14:25:00z, 50.8N/2.8W, 063°) with a profile ascent (P6) to FL160, and continued (14:26:08z, 084°) as SLR Run 6 (-9.21/-7.74°C, 548mbar). CPI again reported regions of liquid cloud (ie supercooled water), with sudden changes to fully glaciated cloud. Flight Manager reported a large drop in side-slip parameters and that the turbulence probe was now definitely “iced up”. Towards the end of R6 CPI reported plates and stellar crystals. CT was observed at certain times too. At the end of R6 (14:33:53z, 51.09N/1.8W, 548mbar), temperatures were again warmer at -8.09/-8.43°C.

The next outbound leg commenced (14:38:07z, 51.1N/1.7W) with a profile ascent (P7) to FL170, and continued at that level as Run 7 (14:39:01z, 51.0N/1.7W, 240°). CPI reported small drops and large drops but not much ice at the start (T/Td = -9.75/ -9.58°C, 527mbar), and later reported mixed phase while 2D noted it had observed “big round objects”. Following a brief hole in the cloud, CPI reported plates and aggregates of plates. At the end of R7 (14:51:08z, 50.8N/3.0W, 251°) temperatures were again lower by half a degree. CPI reported large crystals, and large numbers of small ice crystals, and questioned if this was due to crystal break-up. 2DP/2DC observed concentrations of 3.9/50 per litre respectively.

The return in-bound leg commenced with profile P8 (14:54:55z, 50.9N/2.8W, 084°) up to FL180 which started near to CT but then continued in cloud until the aircraft had to interrupt the profile to take immediate action to avoid 2 fast military aircraft approaching from above. P8 ended and Run 8 continued at FL180 (15:01:13z, 51.0N/2.4W, 088°) still in-cloud at -12.12/-11.53°C (505mbar) and extended to track overhead of Chilbolton (15:08:17z).

The final outbound leg started (at 15:12:34z, 51.1N/1.4W) with the last profile ascent P9 to FL190 again passing overhead of Chilbolton. At FL190, P9 ended and Run 9 started (15:13:37z, 51.1N/1.5W, 232°) just above cloud tops (-13.25/-15.73°C, 485mbar). The leg was largely cloud free apart from a few wispy regions (and the

rear facing camera was seen to be frozen over) and was terminated early (15:22:01z, 50.9N/2.5W, 252°) to ensure a final incloud return leg could be made.

The final inbound leg was carried out at FL150 – calculated to be in the middle of the Hallet-Mossop region. A non-profile descent was made down to this level, and R10 commenced at 15:27:14z (50.9N/2.2W, 088°), where temperatures were –6.27/-6.21°C (571mbar). R10 ended at 15:32:59z (51.0N/1.5W).

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KETH BOWER

CWVC

Flight No **B.117A**.....

Date **27/07/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
08:55:19	BST (KUB)				T/O
					CB 1000' ~200' thick
					Next cloud layer - in at 4600'
08:08:40	≡ 9:08 45 KUB BST				MOXAEE DISPLAY TIME.
08:11:10					9200' - CT on ascent to 10000'
08:12:50				51.9/1.5W	In-gap in cloud layer 6m/s/187° 1.41°/0.38° 261kt
08:13:50			189	51.8/1.6W	OP1 first melted ice crystal
					expect 2600' based base on profile
		FL100			1.93/0.37°C 676
08:21:49	P1 ↓	FL100-8600	156	51.3/1.5W	
08:24:55	P1 int	FL70			
08:25:53	P1 re				
					3700' - into CT.
					12000' 60nm out from Chulballeh
					no cloud under 36 GHz - ∴ No overhead ray
08:30:33	P1 and	2600'			CAMERA is working
08:30:59	P2	2600 ↑			
08:40:25	P2 int	12000			Cloud at this alt -1.4 / -7.9° 8 m/s / 245°
08:45:50	P2 recm	FL120 ↑	75	50.8/2.6W	-1.32 / -8.65 13m/s / 230 253kt
					No cloud above - ∴ need to abort
					But more than 1 hr of fuel left to burn
08:54:17	P2 int	FL200		51.0/1.6W	26m/s / 211° 464kt -16.83 / -16.97
08:57:18	P2 int	FL200 → 240		51.0/1.7W	Some wispy Ci above.

09:01:11 P2 and FL240 252 50.9/2.2W -25.5 / -42.96 392 22m/s / 230

(About CWVC flight at this point)

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER CWVC

Flight No B.117A

Date 27/07/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					→ FL260 ^{or higher} - 10 mins full profile to 50'
					10 mins at 100' - BB R test
09:05:30		FL240	260	50.9/2.7	21m/s/232 -24.82/-43.05 392mb
09:07:19					descending to FL230 to cross aural
09:08:40	Trans	FL230	265	50.8/3.1	Photo 21m/s/228 409mb -23.4°C/-37.2°C
					FL330 max alt required.
09:12:12	Climb	to FL330	263	50.8/3.8	
09:15:05	Climb	F255	268	50.8/3.9	-29.4°/-39.04° 23m/s/230 361mb
09:16:40					Photo RWS
09:17:30	Climb	FL280	265	50.9/4.2	-35.87/-35.01 29/230 327mb
09:2		FL300	264		CI is just above us - around us -
09:23:05	Climb	FL300	245	50.8/5.0W	-42.88°C/-44.2 32/217 294mb
					Ice crystal
09:27:36	Run 1	FL320	244	50.7/5.5	31m/s/222°
					CPI - near top of climb - same problem as per usual.
					274mb -47.7/-48.1 354kts 31/219
09:32:20					Can see through CT - 2D seems grouped !!
09:32:37	P1 end			50.6/6.1W	CPI - Brossella 2D - dendritic?
					only see dendrite around -15°C - P.C.
09:36:06	P3 ↓	FL320			
09:44:15	P3	FL233	59	51.0/4.5	Photo RWS Ci
09:45:30					Photo LWS Ci
09:46:46					CPI will re-land in this clear air section
09:47:50	P3 cont	FL200	60	51.2/4.1W	-17.3°C/-26.91°C 465mb

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci : KEITH BOWEN

CWVC

Flight No **B.117A**.....

Date **27/07/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:50:29	P3 rec	FL200	240	51.2/4.2W	-17.49/-23.99 Kent/226' 476mb CPI probe temps - normal
09:52:55					Tail decoupling an - stop any problems decoupling through dead
					13:30 launch from above airfield - Corbett quickly turnaround - Fire cover at Cranhill - Sp...
10:08:58	P3 int	4000'			1002 QDM. - in cloud here
10:10:31		4000'	213	50.6/6.0W	5mb/130° 10.38/11.11°C 864mb 226kts 2DC - seeing bits of the O CPI nowt - problem
10:15:53	P3 rec	from 4000'			CPI back on line
10:18:03	P3 end	start Run 2 @ 2600'			
10:20:30	R2	2600'	02	50.6/5.3W	4m/s/130° 12.09/11.63° 909mb (ETA Cran: 12:25 local) 2D - v small drops N of 12 (has been 50k) CPI seeing a little - not much
10:28:16	R2 end				Climbng to Transit back at FL110
	trans	10000	50	51.1/4.3W	1.55/-0.59°C 7m/s/223° 652mb 248kts
10:33:20	trans	FL110	51	51.2/4.2W	-0.36°/-2.68°C 5m/s/228 670kts 260kts
10:46:45	trans	FL110	52	51.8/28W	Beem -1.11/-0.74° 8/229 at (CT.) Weather 13:00 local 710 13:30 and 17:00

small water leak from NO₂ sys. - reservoir not decoupled either

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci: KEITH BOWEN

ENVC

Flight No **B.117B...**

Date **27/07/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:59:00	KNB B5T				T/O
					CB 1350' out of cloud
13:14:44	Trans	FL100	243	52.2/0.5W	8m/s/225° 144°/0.35°C 696mb. CPC - AMS - not measuring on either unit
13:24:00	Trans	FL100	176	51.8/1.7W	Clear air at this alt - whil - heading south - clouds
13:28:00	Trans	FL100		51.6/1.7W	Clear of cloud again 13 - 19.5 kPa. CPI - melting level
13:35:17	Run 3	FL100			Outbound from CHB → West bound by alt 10k Wpl snow 2D -
		FL100	258		Radar is down - on air own
13:37:45	Run 3	FL100	253	51.0/1.7W	CPI - frozen drops 1.21"/0.78° 6m/s/252° 696mb
13:44:59	R3	FL100	254	50.9/2.4W	0.80°/0.56° 3m/s/253 246kt 696mb mixed phase cloud - poss ice phase melting & shedding LW. - CPI
13:47:35	R3	FL100			Flight Man - 1° center this end of Run.
13:47:55	R3	FL400	253		Heavy rain as coming towards end
13:49:30	R3 end	FL100		50.8/2.0W	Heavy rain - Radar Break on 0.13°/1.28° 5m/s/145° 696mb.
13:51:47					large particles - wet snow 6.5mm across
13:					Tail descing on now.
13:53:16	P4	FL100-FL130	68°	50.9/2.5W	Inbound.
	P4	12000'	76	50.9/2.6W	-253 / 2.07 641 mb
13:50:13	P4 end	FL130	77	50.9/2.5W	-4.23/-3.6°C 10m/s/211° 619mb 260kt

R4 start

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sc. KEITH BOWER.

Flight No **B.117.5**

Date 27/07/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					CT status 6km 14.5kft based 9km - name
					mic needles/columns
					CT @ 20-60km range - 4km
14:01:00		FL130	80	51.0/2.0W	CPJ - columns + liquid patches rained columns
					-3.63/-3.24° 10m/s/199° 619mb 240kt
14:03:16	R4 end	FL130		51.0/1.7W	CPJ - back to liquid plus now - 2D Agassiz (w 2' change + at Eastward)
14:07:36	PS st	FL130-150	246	51.0/1.7W	Outboard probe down Ice detected. FL147
14:09:56	PS end RS start	FL150	249	51.0/1.9W	-6.9°C/6.4°C 15m/s/207° 572mb 265kt
14:12:12	RS int.	FL150		50.9/2.2W	ATC interrupt.
14:13:07	RS rec.	FL150	264		571mb -6.95/-6.76°C
					CPJ - now mostly glaciated cloud Small thin ice on C Phys during prod.
14:17:10	RS.	FL150	244	50.9/2.7W	Also the 2d region - DADSENAC => good con
14:20:00	RS end	FL150		50.8/2.9W	-7.55°/-6.56° glimpses of CT. - 2D seems snow now.
14:20:48	RS end	FL150	247	50.6/3.0W	-7.46/-6.25° 9m/s/232° 572mb 258kt just in tops as go through beam cannot d turb probe penetrative - gone at track - icing (A ice on tip CVI probe) both SIDs have ice on them - ice on wing
14:25:00	PG st	FL150-160	63°	50.6/2.8W	-8.41/-7.55° 17m/s 202
14:26:08	PG end/R6	FL160	84°	50.9/2.7W	-9.21/-7.74 16m/s/202 548mb 262kt

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER

CWVC

Flight No **B.117.B**.....

Date **27/07/05**.....

Page **3** of **4**.....

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					CPI liquid cloud - SC H2O.
14:30:30	R6	FL160	71	51.0/2.2	CPI - glaciated cloud - sudden change S48
					17m/s / 207
				Flight Man.	large drop in side ship pressure - debris
					iced up. - turb probe debris ice over.
					glaciated - CPI - new SC H2O
14:33:32					minute long - plates / stellar.
					breaking out of CT.
14:33:53	R6 end	FL160	80	51.0/1.8W	-8.07°/-8.43° 24m/s/215 264kt
14:36:07	R7 st	FL160-170	240	51.1/1.7W	-7.75°/-8.12° 19m/s/216 S48nb 264kt
14:39:01	R7 end/R7 st	FL170		51.0/1.7W	-9.75°/-9.58°
					CPI - drops (small) + large drops - not much
14:39:58	R7	FL170	250	51.0/1.8W	temp out of cloud
14:40:50	R7	FL170	248	51.0/1.9W	-9.71°/-10.01° 19m/s/218° S27mb. 272kt
14:42:50	R7				CPI - mixed phase 2D - big round objects now (1 minute ago)
14:45:21	R7	FL170	249	50.9/2.4W	-10.27°/-8.73° 18m/s/210° S27mb. 263kt
14:46:05	R7	FL170	250	50.9/2.4W	- brief hole in cloud -
14:51:05	R7				Plates + aggregates of plates - CPI
14:51:08	R7 end	FL170	251	50.8/3.0W	-9.62°/-12.03° 14m/s/255° S27mb
					CPI - large particles - lot of faint snowflakes
					pass Xtal Break up.
					and 3900/m ³ 2DP (average 2000)
					50 / liter 2DP (average 300)
14:54:55	P8 stall	FL170-180	84°	50.9/2.8W	In CT's

14:55:57 P8 int - swirling action
P8 end

-12.28°/-11.2° 14m/s/247° 511mb

14:57:00 - strong swirling action - 2 fast jets

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B117

Date: 27/7/05

Operator: JT / BW training

Page1 of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:06:00											SID2 not crashed log prog says Probe not powered up.
08:21:48	27	0.09	966	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Start Profile 1 descent FL 100
08:23:08	33	0.07	966	10	0	0	0	133	1000	1	FL90
08:24:05	12	0.08	966	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL80
08:24:58	21	0.08	966	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL70 p1 interupt
08:25:53	41	0.07	966	0	1	800	1	383	800	1	Re commence p1 FL70
08:27:07	12	0.07	966	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL60
08:28:05	6	0.07	966	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL50
08:29:04	28	0.07	966	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL40
08:30:18	259	0.26	966	1000	79	50	1	0	0	0	FL30 P1 end
08:30:59	125	0.09	981	1000	500	250	1	33	200	1	Start P2 climb FL26
08:32:25	22	0.07	982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL40
08:33:25	15	0.07	982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL50
08:34:30	6	0.07	982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL60
08:35:28	17	0.06	982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL70
08:36:27	10	0.08	982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL80
08:37:19	19	0.07	982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL90
08:38:29	21	0.06	982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL100
08:39:24	19	0.06	982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL110
08:40:26	7	0.06	982	0	0	0	0	0	00	0	FL120 P2 interrupt
08:45:51	22	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	P2 Restart FL 120
08:46:51	8	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL130
08:47:49	11	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL140
08:48:52	13	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL150
08:49:55	9	0.07	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL160
08:51:01	8	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL170
08:52:07	6	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL180
08:53:16	12	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL190
08:54:19	4	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	P2 interrupt FL200
08:57:19	9	0.08	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	P2 restart FL200

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B117

Date: 27/07/05

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
08:58:18	1	0.07	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL210
08:59:16	2	0.09	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL220
09:00:07	9	0.09	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL230
09:01:12	4	0.09	1045	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL240 P2 end
		End of	science								
09:27:37	16	0.49	0 restarted	100	130	200	8	noise			Start run 1 FL320
09:30:23	28	0.41	1	100	37	225	8	Noise			
09:32:40	10	0.43	4	100	207	225	8	noise			End of run 1
09:36:08	3	0.22	7	10	15	200	4				Start p3 decent FL320
09:37:19	6	0.17	8	75	14	225	8				FL310
09:38:19	7	0.08	8	0	0	0	0				FL300
09:39:19	6	0.09	8	0	0	0	0				FL290
09:40:15	15	0.11	8	0	0	0	0				FL280
09:41:15	12	19	8	100	43	225	10				FL270
09:42:15	21	0.1	8	0	0	0	0				FL260
09:43:04	22	0.09	8	0	0	0	0				FL250
09:43:56	14	0.08	8	0	0	0	0				FL240
09:44:49	24	0.08	8	0	0	0	0				FL230
09:45:50	24	0.08	8	0	0	0	0				FL220
09:46:46	12	0.08	8	0	0	0	0				FL210
09:47:52	29	0.08	8	0	0	0	0				FL200 interrupt P3
09:50:31	22	0.08	8	0	0	0	0				Restart P3 FL200
09:51:34	23	0.08	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL190
09:52:28	37	0.07	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL180
09:53:25	40	0.08	8	0	00	0	0	0	0	0	FL170
09:54:20	51	0.08	8	00	0	0	0	0	0	00	FL160
09:55:17	33	0.08	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL150
09:56:20	44	0.08	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL140
09:57:24	14	0.08	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL130
09:58:28	31	0.08	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	FL120

CLLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B117B

Date: 27/7/05

Operator: JT

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G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
13:35:18	21	0.17	207	10	1	800	2	441	2000	2	Start run 3 FL100
13:37:00	15	0.23	542	100	28	575	2	3422	3000	2	
13:39:00	26	0.21	218	100	58	750	8 mp	1275	4000	8 mp	MP – MIXED PHASE
13:41:00	19	0.12	224	75	16	700	8 mp	733	100	8 mp	
13:43:00	25	0.17	237	100	13.5	600	8 mp	2158	2000	8 mp	
13:45:00	46	0.35	246	100	44	700	8 mp	3025	3500	8 mp	
13:47:00	19	0.4	272	1000	23	550	8 mp	1983	4000	8 mp	
13:49:37	10	0.61	318	1000	51	775	8 mp	5925	6000	8 mp	End of run 3
13:53:15	19	0.72	286	750	221	725	8	8091	6000	8	Start P4 FL100
13:54:23	18	0.63	422	800	248	800	8	12150	4000	8	FL110
13:55:17	84	0.76	440	1000	343	725	8	22533	3000	8	FL120
13:56:13	160	1	460	1000	456	800	8	29291	2000	8	End P4 start run 4 FL130
13:58:00	22	0.71	497	750	190	800	5/6	3808	1000	5/6	
14:00:00	33	1.18	534	1000	112	750	5/6	7550	800	5/6	
14:03:16	60	0.9	562	750	710	550	8	1350	1000	5/6	End run 4
14:07:38	69	0.78	620	1000	253	300	11	1183	400	11	P5 FL130
14:08:53	27	0.4	631	750	8	450	3	266	1000	3	FL140
14:09:56	10	0.74	671	1000	23	400	3	108	600	3	FL150 end of P5 start run 5
14:11:00	3	0.78	689	1000	100	200	3	566	600	3	
14:12:12	6	0.93	727	1000	178	625	3	4933	1000	3	Interrupt Run 5
14:14:13	24	0.9	739	100	155	750	8	3316	3000	3	Recommence Run 5
14:16:00	17	1.01	755	1000	66	750	8	4858	4000	3	
14:18:00	25	1.08	777	400	137	775	8	19725	2000	3	
14:20:48	22	1.09	808	900	331	775	8	219098	3000	3	End run 5
14:24:59	102	1.03	846	1000	530	800	8	70266	2000	3	Start P6 FL150
14:26:05	38	0.82	860	1000	30	750	8	1666	5000	3	End P5 FL160 start of run 6
14:28:00	220	0.7	924	3000	89	800	8	416	1000	8	
14:30:00	10	1.15	960	100	5	450	8	516	4000	8	Looks like some large sphericals
14:32:00	37	0.7	981	3000	100	775	8	633	5000	8	
14:33:53	13	0.09	1010	3	0	0	0	25	900	8	End of run 6
14:38:09	9	0.08	1025	10	0	0	0	91	1000	8	Start of P7 FL160
14:39:01	16	0.09	1025	100	11	225	8	1141	800	8	End P7 FL170 start run 7

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B117B

Date: 27/07/05

Operator: JT

Page of

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
14:41:00	6	0.46	1039	3	2	800	8	91	800	8	
14:43:00	12	0.7	1052	3000	21	800	8	75	3000	8	
14:45:00	13	0.28	1078	3000	1	650	8	91	1000	8	
14:47:00	1	0.49	1108	1000	362	575	8	416	800	8	
14:49:00	15	0.84	1150	2000	69	800	3	2308	1000	3	Angular particles maybe fragments
14:51:10	13	0.13	1154	100	51	650	3	3900	800	3	End of run 7
14:54:54	14	0.18	1157	1000	7.5	750	3	1666	2000	3	Start P8 FL170
14:56:	29	0.8	1171	1191	Evasive			action	cant	Type	End of P8 FL180 start run 8
					Off track						Run interrupted
15:01:11	9	0.81	1240	5000	223	800	8	483	1000	8	Recommence run 8
15:03:00	11	1.08	1290	2000	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:05:00	192	0.77	1332	1000	46	75	11	50	400	11	
15:07:00	12	0.81	1402	1000	1	0	8	116	400	11	
15:08:50	9	0.88	1475	1000	0	0	0	175	1000	8	End of run 8
15:12:35	11	0.77	1611	1000	2	400	8	50	400	8	Start P9 FL180
15:13:38	11	0.07	1634	0	0	0	0	Noise			FL190 end P9 start run 9
15:15:00	17	0.07	1634	0	0	0	0	Noise			
15:17:00	12	0.08	1635	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:19:00	7	0.07	1635	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
15:22:01	12	0.2	1635	100	2	800	3	4733	800	3	end of run 9
15:27:14	7	0.8	1663	100	3.5	200	8	50	400	11	Start run 10 FL150
15:29:00	2	0.07	1680	0	0	0	0	33	1000	11	
15:31:00	53	0.14	1711	500	196	800	8	7633	1000	8	
15:32:59	7	0.83	1751	1000	7	800	8	300	3000	8	End of run 10
Problem	processin	FFSSP	data								

27/7/05 3117
Wednesday

1 of 8

0730 - Power on - windows on CPI seem dirty

Get image mem to 117 - Good

PDS DC levels

95	4.7	
90	6.2	- 8.2 (intermittent)

757 : Cloud base quite low.

8.03 : Nice droplet cloud.

8.13 : Melting ice particles - is water being shed from the ice?

Start of profile 1 082148

nothing to report really - just droplets

Interrupt 082456

Resume profile 082553

just droplets.

End profile 1 083031

Start profile 2

083059

2 of 8

Fallen with CPC 3025
- left rack

845 back @ rack

Stop ~~profile~~ profile @ 084026

Resume profile 2 after time

084550

- Mention that flight maybe abandoned as there is no cloud above the freezing level.

Interrupt profile 2

085412

Resume profile 2

085712

Nothing!

End profile 2

090112

Flight plan changed to BBR test?

height 320 - problem started with CPI

Run 1

092737

930 - all temperature readings are very cold - have heaters switched off?

End Run 1

093238

Start profile 3

093608

See if probe rights itself in descent

Interrupt

094752

Resonance

095031

1001 problem with background algorithm no data

1010 - Probe has been of line for 10 mins

- ~~image mean very~~
 BQ algorithm failing - lowered min
 image mean to 50 ^{from 60} & probe got a
 BQ but BQ mean 55

missed some logging time here...

Reconnect profile 3

101553

1015 CPI on line

End profile 3

101805

Start Run 2

101805

- 1020

interesting - the # of frms / second
was 40 but hardly any images were
showing => perhaps this is due to vibration?

End Run 2

102817

Return to cranfield.

B117 B

Catch the end of the foul @ Chibbolton

- Power went down suddenly - UPS started beeping.
 - Powered down CPI/ADA PC's just in case UPS failed.
- 1245 - Restarted computer & software.
-

1301 droplet cloud.

1306 - ~~to~~ Lots of wall paper couldn't get background so turned up PDS thresholds momentarily

1322 ↑ went to try and help with CPC but ~~so~~ don't know how to use it anyway - Keith; perhaps pump is broken.

1333 - Melting level

Rin 3

1335/8

1337 . very strange frozen droplets
raining

End run 3

134937

6 of 8

Profile 4

135275

135317

lots of poly crystal

end

135615

Run 4

135615

columns

columns are rimed.

droplets

End 4

140316

Start profile 5

140738

liquid, mostly

End profile 5

140956

Start run 5

140956

Interrupted.

141212

Run 5
~~Run 5~~

resume

141310

~~Run 5~~

mixed phase then granulated cloud

End

run 5

142048

1423 — some fragments.

Start profile 6 142501

Nice habits

End profile 6 142607

Start run 6 "

— liquid cloud — then glaciated fairly quickly

End run 6 ~~1433~~ 143453

Start profile 7 143809

not.

End p 7 143904

Start run 7 143904

not much cloud — most liquid

mostly liquid, with occasional ice

— fragments?

End run 7 145110

Start profile 8 145455

End profile 8 145600

↳ Avoiding air traffic many see hammers

Start Run 8

150113

8 of 8

End Run 8

150851

Start profile 9

151235

End profile 9

151338

Start run 9

151338

1520

- new tunnel

rained, plates, aggregates, rounded

End 9

152201

"None stretch"

Start Run 10

152716

End Run 10

153239

1540

- Ramped up both threshold &
POS thresholds to take a background
- Then put back to normal.

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B117**

Date: 27/07/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	<u>Probes</u>		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	Y
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	<u>Racks:</u>		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	Y	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	N
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	Y
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO	N		Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	Y
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	N
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	N
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	N			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B117

Date: 27/07/05

Instruments

1. Link to HORACE – initially okay but then couldn't open iExplorer pages and no update info on DECterm window. (HORACE was accessed via Console window on pre-flight which may have caused the problem). Rebooted HORACE then okay.
2. CCN – u/s from yesterday's flight. No baseline or detector signal. Some progress on this during flight but still not working properly. Found baseline to be adjusted way out of its range and also a loose connection. Got it working for the 2nd flight.
3. AMS CPC – reading zero during initial profile, couldn't get it working.
4. Satcom H – front handset used a couple of times then nothing shown on display when dialling further numbers and calls not completed. Aft handset working normally. After 2nd T/O, front handset working again.
5. INU – “INU in Initiated BIT” momentary message on status page 1 after T/O 2. Later “CDU Fail”. Otherwise okay.
6. Turb Probe – possibly iced over briefly at 1358. AOSS check & diff paras dropped out but recovered within a minute to previous values(FL130). At FL150, AOA check para drifted downwards and AOSS upwards, probable icing. Ice apparent on SID probes and canister blank. At FL160, both AOSS paras suddenly dropped.

Status of other instruments

CPI - Same problem with temperatures display at high level though might have a solution now, can test it on next flight. No data lost on scientific runs. (Problem after CWVC part of flight).

Cloud Physics – SID 2 not working, can run software without pc rebooting itself now

NOxy leak – water reservoir on aft rack, middle shelf overflowing gently down rack and onto floor. May be that reservoir wasn't drained after yesterday's flight. Dave Stewart informed.

CVI - ok

Other problems – weather not suitable on arrival at Chilbolton, no freezing cloud. May return later today to try again.

Aircraft

1. Lost science power on 2nd departure from Cranfield. Started No 1 & 4 engines, power transfer to a/c then reversed back. Power lost during subsequent startup checks. Shutdown CVI, Core chem etc. Start No. 2 & 3 then re-establish Science Power, then okay.

Satcom H Calls – 4 FAAM/CWVC, 1DFL

New plot, same times

Flight B117 15:38:03

Heading 337 deg Speed 369 knots Height 15.0kft Press 570mb

Lat 51.5N Long 1.7W Wind 12 ms-1/ 199 deg

Temp -7.19C Dewpoint -6.54C

From 13:00:00 to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT
 PRESSURE HEIGHT

56283 secs
 15.04 Kft

⊙ Alt
 ○